

Helping Neglected and Abused Children With Expert Assistance

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Abstract

A person who has not yet attained physical, social, or emotional adulthood is a kid. Up to the age of 18, everyone is treated as if they are still children. To guarantee that the kid grows up healthy in every manner and develops a good personality from the time they are born, the conditions of safe attachment and positive contact with the family must be satisfied. Regrettably, there are a substantial number of families that do not satisfy these requirements. These events unequivocally demonstrate the need of devoting a greater amount of focus and energy to the safeguarding of children and families today. Children are put in a position where they are more susceptible to neglect and abuse because of migration from rural regions to urban areas, economic challenges, as well as physical and mental health problems. Under the umbrella term of "child neglect and abuse," all forms of violence perpetrated against children across the globe are analyzed. Abuse and neglect of children may take many forms, including physical, sexual, emotional, and financial abuse. It is a well-established truth that children who are neglected or abused suffer from negative impacts that may last a lifetime. Hence, to accurately diagnose and treat cases of child neglect and abuse, professionals working in this sector should have a solid understanding of the moral and legal duties they have, and they should be

particularly skilled in their ability to communicate with children. In addition to the therapeutic responsibilities that fall within their purview, professionals are obligated to report children who have been neglected or abused to the appropriate authorities. In this scenario, the professional assistance that the children will get is of the utmost importance for them to learn what steps to take during and after instances of neglect and abuse, as well as to readjust to regular life. Throughout the course of this research, fundamental information on abused and neglected children will be presented. The significance of aiding these youngsters is dissected, from a neutral point of view, in the presence of knowledgeable individuals.

Keywords: *Child, Neglect, Abuse, Expert, Help*

1. Introduction

It is believed that there are a limited number of social screening studies on the prevalence of neglect and abuse cases during childhood in Turkey, and the reason for this is that there are inadequacies in revealing, clarifying, and reporting the cases. This is one of the reasons why it is believed that there are a limited number of social screening studies. (Bahar, Savaş, 2009, p. 12) Abandonment of children is a significant social issue. It is possible to characterize it as the failure to satisfy required requirements in the sense of growth, as well as the failure of the family to fulfill their obligations towards and to care for the kid (WHO, 1999, p. 5) Children who are neglected are unable to develop emotionally, socially, physically, or linguistically, and as a consequence, they are unable to grow in a manner that is conducive to their health. The behaviors that fall under the category of neglect include the following: failing to meet the child's physical and emotional needs in an adequate manner, failing to provide necessary treatment, failing to fulfill the duty of providing counseling to the child as a parent, and leaving the child alone. The areas of health, education, physical and emotional development, nutrition, housing, and safe living circumstances are some of the places where these requirements may manifest themselves. The socio-economic resources that a parent has available have a role in determining how seriously the obligations are taken. It is not always straightforward to tell the difference between neglect and abuse. The primary characteristic that sets them apart from one another is that abuse is an active behavior, while neglect is a passive one. (Dereobalı, Çırak Karadağ and Sonmez, 2013, s. 50) The term "mental trauma" captures

neglect the most accurately. Abuse of all kinds—emotional, physical, and sexual—is almost often the next step after this circumstance. It is exceedingly difficult to make a diagnosis of neglect since it is a more nebulous term than abuse. A kid's psychosocial and mental health might suffer when other members of his or her family do not provide enough care for the youngster at home. Children who have developmental and growth retardation, who struggle with social adaption, whose educational requirements are not satisfied, and who do not benefit from health services have an increased risk of being neglected. On the other hand, child abuse refers to all the actions that can be conducted by parents, adults, other members of the community, and the state, either intentionally or unintentionally, in a way that hinders the growth of the child in the areas of socialization, emotional development, linguistic ability, and physical development. The term "child abuse" may mean different things in different societies. Abuse refers to the practice of knowingly subjecting a kid to one or more harmful actions, which may take many forms. When it comes to abuse, the conduct in question needs to be banned and ought to be stopped rather than causing damage. (Ünal,2008, s. 18)

2. Neglected and Abused Children

A person who has not yet attained physical, social, or emotional adulthood is a kid. A kid is somebody who is less than 18 years old. This definition includes everyone. From the time he or she is born, the kid begins to create the foundations of his or her personality and mental structure via the fulfillment of his or her developmental requirements and the successful communication skills he or she learns with his or her family. For the sake of the children's overall well-being and development, it is critical that this process be effectively managed. Under the umbrella term "Child Neglect and Abuse," we classify a wide variety of harmful actions that are conducted against young people (Polat, 1999, s. 6) Behaviors that fall under the umbrella of neglect and abuse are behaviors that have a detrimental impact on every aspect of a child's growth and development. Abuse of children often occurs at the hands of adults such as the child's parents, other adults in the household, or even babysitters. In most cases, the neglecting or abusing of children is caused by a society's value judgements, conventional attitudes, and the sociocultural factors of the society. (Güler, Uzun, Boztaş ve Aydoğan, 2002, s. 128)

2.1. Neglect and Abuse Risk Factors

Characteristics of Parents Who Neglect and Abuse Children; The previous experiences of the parents are the most fundamental trait that may be detected in their children. It is impossible for parents to build solid bonds with their children if they themselves were victims of abusive conduct when they were children. As a result, these families will never be able to maintain a loving connection between the members of the household. In addition to this, these parents do not serve as a positive example of appropriate conduct toward their children. They typically only know one model of conduct, and that is the paradigm of abusive treatment. At times of struggle, frustration, or stress in their life, people may model their behavior after the model of hitting, assaulting, or utterly ignoring their children by abandoning them to fend for themselves and leaving them alone. The reason for this is because they have had their own parents to serve as an example for them.

Lack of having adequate information; It is essential for people, prior to having a kid, to have knowledge about the entire process that occurs before, during, and after the birth of the child, and to create a road plan in accordance with this information. If not, it can be observed that parents who are unable to conduct this procedure in the proper manner constitute a danger in terms of the abuse and neglect of their children. The communication patterns that are established in the family in which he or she is born are indicative of how he or she will behave as a parent in the years to come. A kid who is brought up by a mother or father who was neglected or mistreated as a child will pass on similar habits to their offspring, which may have detrimental effects.

Being young; Individuals are considered mature both physically and mentally when they reach the age of marriage. One of the risk factors for neglect and abuse is the fact that the parents are too young to manage the responsibilities that they have. Although though teenagers are physically capable of having children, they are unable to fully assume the responsibilities of parents since their mental development has not caught up to their physical development. Both, as well as the children who have yet to be born, are going to suffer a great deal from the effects of this predicament.

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Unplanned Pregnancy: The first step that must be essential for the person to grow in a healthy manner is the procedure of a pregnancy that has been planned. In the absence of contraception, unintended births may put a strain on the emotional connection that a child has with both their mother and their father.

Single parent: In the event of parental divorce or separation, long-term employment of one parent outside of the city or nation, or the passing of a parent, the surviving parent may not be able to assume full responsibility for the upbringing of their kid. The parent is left to navigate this procedure on their own since their own family does not provide a support structure for them. It is possible that the kid will suffer from neglect since the only parent in a household that is struggling financially needs to find employment.

Low level of education; Parents who have a low level of socioeconomic education typically have insufficient knowledge about the physical, emotional, social, and language development of their children. As a result, these parents typically are not open to self-improvement and tend to repeat the methods that they learned in their own families.

Environmental conditions of the family; Children are more likely to be neglected or abused when their parents' living circumstances cause them to feel increased levels of tension and worry. This in turn raises the risk that the children will be neglected or abused.

Self-perception of parents; Children who do not spend their childhoods engaging in healthy forms of attachment and trust develop a sense that they are unwanted and worthless. When they are adults, this circumstance has a detrimental impact on their socio-cultural position as well as their marital life. Often, people decide to have a family so that they may have someone who will love and care for them. If the kid does not live up to these standards that the parents have set for them, the parents will be dissatisfied. As a direct consequence of this, neglect and abuse occur in a sequential order. (Beyazit, Ayhan, 2015, s. 443)

Marriage problems: Some of the causes of child neglect and abuse include parents who do not get along with one another and who engage in frequent arguments and heated conversations in the house.

Mental disorders: Those who suffer from mental disorders, who are unable to deal with mental issues, or who have mental retardation are more prone to neglect or mistreat their children. (Cüceloğlu, 1996, s.56)

2.2. Types of Neglect and Abuse

Neglect and Abuse can be divided into 4 categories.

- Physical Neglect and Abuse
- Sexual Neglect and Abuse
- Psychological-Emotional Neglect and Abuse
- Economic Neglect and Abuse (Keser, Odabaş, Elibüyük, 2010, s. 150)

3. Physically Neglected and Abused Children

The use of physical force, aggression, or injury on the part of an adult who is responsible for the care and needs of the kid (such as the mother, the father, the babysitter, etc.) or an outsider is physical abuse. (Erdoğan, Aslan, 2020, s. 104) Physical neglect occurs when a parent fails to provide their kid with essentials such as love, attention, affection, nourishment, shelter, safety, cleanliness, health, and education. Other forms of neglect include emotional neglect and sexual neglect. One of the most significant challenges of our day is the prevalence of cases of neglect and abuse on a physical level. Every single youngster who is subjected to abuse is also put in dangerous situations. On the other hand, some experts believe that violence is a kind of self-defense for those who engage in violent behavior, and other experts believe that violent behavior is a necessary phenomenon for those who engage in violent behavior. While there have been many ways established to explain the reasons why children are subjected to physical neglect and abuse, none of these approaches are adequate on their own to explain the reasons why children are subjected to physical neglect and abuse. On the other hand, it has been observed that parents who utilize physical neglect and abuse towards their children were themselves subjected to the same behaviors while they were growing up. Those who are not properly accepted in society, who have mental difficulties, who are in a tough socio-economic condition, and who are unable to create healthy connection within the family are more likely to have functional disorders in their life. As a direct consequence of this, the most prevalent kind of harmful conduct in today's society is physical neglect and abuse (also known as violence) directed at children. Neglecting or abusing a person's body physically may result in mental

health issues, cognitive-psychological diseases, and even death. (Bekci,2006, s.23) When we talk about physical neglect, we're referring to things like a lack of care and affection, failure to ensure cleanliness and safety, deprivation of shelter, clothing, food and drink, health and education, and so on. When we talk about physical abuse, however, we're talking about direct violence. It has been discovered that forced marriages are more successful in families where there is a history of physical abuse since these households are more likely to suffer difficulties such as conflict and disagreement between spouses. According to the findings of the research, some of the causes for physical abuse include the fact that one of the parents is a stepparent, a lack of joint decision-making about the children, health and financial issues, and so on. The mother, the father, or other adults in the household may be the perpetrators of physical abuse inside the family. At school, the perpetrators may be instructors, other authorities, or even students themselves. (Otterman, Lainpelto, Lindblad, 2013, s. 1199)

3.1. Symptoms and Consequences of Physical Neglect and Abuse

If the child is not developing at the same rate as his or her peers, if his or her cleaning needs are not met, if he or she is not dressed appropriately for the season, if he or she is frequently absent from school and his or her absenteeism increases, if he or she expresses discomfort, if he or she has recurrent health problems, if he or she engages in self-harming behaviors, or if he or she has to work, Children who have been neglected are more likely to experience feelings of isolation and vulnerability, as well as insecurity, learning difficulties, aggression or behavioral problems, failure in peer relations and communication, developmental delay, health problems that can lead to death in extremely serious cases, hoarding habits in some children, depressive characteristics, sadness, introversion, and tantrums. If there are signs of physical abuse on the kid's body, such as bruises, wounds, swelling, bites, burns, fractures, dislocations, or cigarette marks, the possibility of the child being abused physically should be considered. It has been shown that children who have been subjected to physical abuse are more likely to use the same abusive tactics on their own offspring in the future. Children who have been subjected to physical abuse often exhibit symptoms such as anxiety, withdrawal, negative self-perception, low self-esteem, increased aggression and violent behaviors, feelings of worthlessness and helplessness, failure in social relations, and the display of behaviors that are forbidden by society. It is unavoidable that children and adolescents who have been subjected

to physical abuse within the context of the family would, at some point in their adult lives, resort to violent behavior against their partners. The development of aggressive and violent behaviors in later life is more prevalent in males than it is in girls because boys are more likely to be physically abused as children.

3.2. Types of Physical Neglect and Abuse

Types of Physical Neglect; Failure to Meet Basic Needs; This occurs when a kid is not fulfilling his or her basic requirements, including as eating, drinking, having a safe place to sleep, and getting an education. Therefore, the child falls physically behind his or her classmates. *Emotional Deprivation* is when a kid does not get the emotional needs that they have, such as love, attention, connection, being with, supporting, or listening to them. It is the failure to satisfy the emotional needs of the child.

Types of Physical Abuse; By beating: The child is beaten with hands, fists or a tool. Symptoms are usually on the head, neck, back and buttocks. Bone fractures or cracks may occur under the areas where bruising is observed. *By burning*: This occurs when the child meets hot water or hot objects because of insufficient attention to the child, which is especially common. *By poisoning*: This occurs when the child takes medication, drinks foreign substances such as detergents, or overdoses on alcohol.

3.3 Helping Physically Abused and Neglected Children with Expert Assistance

A child's fundamental physiological requirements, which include a safe connection, love, attention, tolerance, support, cooperation, shelter, cleaning, feeding, drinking, and overall health, can only be fulfilled within the context of a loving and nurturing family. If these requirements are not addressed, or if the individual is ignored or mistreated, they need psychological rehabilitation, and the family requires guidance in the development of appropriate conduct. Children who have been ignored physically and mistreated should first be approached by the specialist using the watch-listen-connect strategy, which is a 3-part psychological first aid technique. The strategy known as "Game Therapy" is preferable to use

while dealing with children in the early childhood years. When the relationship between the expert and the kid has been formed and the child is at least 10 years old, the specialist should begin individual treatment and provide psychological assistance to the family.

4. Sexually Abused Children

When a person is forced to participate in sexual activity against their will, this is an example of sexual abuse. A kid who has been sexually abused may have been subjected to a variety of sexually abusive activities, including rape, the touching or removal of genital organs, the use of sexually explicit language, the forcing of the child to view pornographic material, and exhibitionism. (Mullen, Martin, Romans ve Herbison,1996, s. 7-21) Children's psychological, social, and cognitive development may be negatively impacted when they are subjected to sexual abuse, whether that abuse occurs inside the home or outside. Children who are subjected to sexual abuse will inevitably have traumatic effects. Both the act of sexual assault and its aftermath may be traumatic. Before and throughout the adolescent years, when sexual growth and changes take place, children are at risk of being exposed to sexually abusive practices. The onset, duration, outcome, and type of behavior related to sexual abuse, as well as the identity of the abuser and the age difference between the child and the abuser, all play a role in determining the sadness, the state of being affected, and the trauma process of the abused adolescent. Other factors that play a role include the age difference between the child and the abuser. During adolescence, the most common forms of sexual abuse that adolescents may be subjected to include exposure, verbal teasing, molestation, and sexual intercourse. Other forms of sexual abuse that adolescents may be subjected to include talking obscenely over the phone or face to face, telling lewd stories, showing pornographic pictures, and talking about sexually explicit topics. As a result of the fact that sexual abuse almost always takes place in private and leaves the victim, whether a child or adolescent, in a state of intense emotional devastation, it is vitally important for families to keep a close eye on their children during this time and to get in touch with them if they notice any changes in their mood. It has been discovered that sexual abuse may be observed at any socioeconomic level. [Citation needed] [Citation needed] Although the incidence of divorce, alcohol and drug abuse, delinquency rate, violence and anti-social behaviors in the family were found to be high in abusers, it was noticed that the rate of depression in the mother was high. This was particularly true of the father. Children are

especially susceptible to being abused because they do not have any wicked tendencies of their own, they trust easily, and they are easily fooled. Abuse of a sexual nature occurs in females three times more often than in boys. (Aksüt, 2020) The feelings of guilt, worry, and terror are the driving forces for the recurrent maltreatment of many children. Abuse of a child's sexuality throughout childhood may result in a wide range of mental, social, sexual, and behavioral issues. Because of this, they find themselves in potentially harmful circumstances, which in turn has a ripple effect on the network of connections in their life. The connection that survivors of sexual abuse establish in their minds between loving and being humiliated, between closeness and being deceived, ultimately leads them into circumstances that are detrimental to their wellbeing. Many people find that engaging in sexual activity and maintaining abusive relationships is their way of loving and being loved. A predisposition toward violence towards their bodies, aggression that is a symptom of both the pain that has been experienced in the past and the suffering that is now being experienced, is often the result of intense emotions of guilt and shame, as well as the associated thoughts of worthlessness.

4.1. Psychological Symptoms of Sexual Abuse

It is possible to talk about psychological symptoms if the child is constantly in a state of negative thinking, has nightmares with sexual content, has trouble falling asleep and is afraid of the dark and sleeping alone, cannot concentrate, has a decreased success rate in his or her studies, suffers from outbursts of anger, exhibits sexual behaviors inappropriate for his or her age, engages in masturbation behaviors and increases in this behavior, constantly plays sexual ga games, and so on. Psychological symptoms can be caused by a...

Psychological symptoms of sexual abuse by age; It is possible to talk about the psychological symptoms of sexual abuse if a baby between the ages of 0 and 2 reacts with eating disorders, fear of strangers, and constant crying; children between the ages of 0 and 3, which we call early childhood education, embarrassment, guilt, anger, helplessness, fear of harm and contamination, regression, withdrawal, enuresis, encopresis, eating and sleeping disorders; or children between the ages of 3 and 6, which we call middle childhood education Behaviors such as aggression, masturbation, fear, shame, guilt, mistrust, helplessness, anger, aggression, fear of harm and contamination, social withdrawal, restlessness/disorder, obsessive-

compulsive disorder, and engaging in sexual games with minors are indicators that a child in the school-age range between the ages of 6 and 12 may have a mental health condition. Fear, anger, shame, insecurity, experiencing conflicts about sexuality and sexual roles within the family, feeling of contamination, helplessness, if they show clear and understandable symptoms such as engaging in sexually provocative behaviors, masturbating in public, constantly having sexually explicit conversations with friends, if depression, suicidal ideation or suicide, fondness for addictive substances, running away from home are present in an adolescent between the ages of 13 and 24. In addition, if they show clear There is a significantly increased risk of sadness and a diminished sense of self-perception among children who have been subjected to sexual abuse. These children and adolescents have a high rate of suicidal ideation as well as attempted suicide. (Yolcuolu, 2010, section 1) Researchers have discovered a link between major depressive disorder symptoms that first appear in adulthood and childhood sexual abuse.

4.2. Medical Symptoms of Sexual Abuse

In children and adolescents, It is possible to talk about medical symptoms such as psychosomatic pains that do not go away despite treatment, oral, anal and vaginal infections, damage to the genitals as a result of repeated masturbation, depression, fear of sexuality or, conversely, excessive sexual behavior, vaginismus, anorexia and bulimia.

4.3. Types of Sexual Abuse

Abuse is any sexual contact with a child against his/her will. Child sexual abuse can be applied by a mother, father, stepmother, stepfather, sibling, relative, teacher, neighbor, friend or stranger. Often when a child is sexually abused, they may have disturbing thoughts, feelings or behaviors. When the child tries to escape from the person who is sexually abusing them or when they object, they may be threatened. If the abuser is a member of the family, the child may hide the incident, thinking that family members will be angry, embarrassed with him/her, and that there will be disintegration within the family. Children who are sexually abused have common characteristics such as low self-esteem, feelings of uselessness, strange thoughts about sex, tendency towards sexuality, introversion, distrust of adults and suicidal tendencies.

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Rape is when a person is forced to have sexual intercourse without their voluntary and informed consent. Many children feel ashamed of what they have been through, dislike themselves for having to endure this shame, and may come to hate their parents for not recognizing what they have been through, for not protecting them, and have difficulty forgiving them. Girls who have been exposed to rape often misbehave in their choice of partners, do not have regular and stable marriages or do not marry at all. Boys may have problems with sexual orientation.

Incest Relationship. Incest is inappropriate sexual intercourse within the family or between relatives. The taboo factor of incest makes it difficult to uncover this abuse. Incestuous relationships commonly take the form of father-daughter, father-son, sister-brother, mother-son, grandmother or grandfather-grandson. It can also occur among other relatives. Data on incest is almost non-existent. The reason for this is that incest is something that is shamed, hidden and covered up with the society. Individuals in incestuous relationships always tend to hide it. This situation increases the abuse and criminality in incestuous relationships and causes the abuse to continue in proportion to the sense of shame and helplessness of the abused. Incestuous relationships are usually revealed when they become a pathological problem and help is sought, or when legal practices come into play due to severe physical conditions. This can cause serious psychological trauma in the abused person. Symptoms suggestive of incest include alcoholic or authoritarian father, absence of a mother, mother's inability to be a protective force in the family, a daughter playing the role of the mother, parents having ended or problematic sexual lives, father's substance abuse, parents who were previously exposed to incest, presence of different relatives at home, living together as an extended family. Symptoms seen in children because of incest include fear, anxiety, regression in skills, aggression, absenteeism from school, decreased school success, finger sucking, nail biting and sleep disorders, withdrawal from the family, desire to be alone, psychosomatic reactions. In pre-adolescents and adolescents, depression, feelings of guilt, criminal tendencies, sexual intercourse with different people and suicidal tendencies may be observed. Unlike other children, abused children grow up with the instinct of shame and concealment. As a result, emotional problems and psychological traumas such as guilt, betrayal, stigmatization, alienation, anger and resentment are inevitable. (İşeri, 2008, s. 470-477)

4.4. Consequences of Sexual Abuse

Childhood sexual abuse causes psychological disintegration and fragmentation. Sexual feelings, attitudes and behaviors may deviate from their normal development in sexually abused children. This may lead to feelings of alienation, emptiness, meaninglessness and suicide. When used for sexual purposes and unable to prevent it, the child will find himself/herself in feelings of helplessness and helplessness and will engage in blaming behavior. The child who is sexually abused sees himself/herself as responsible for his/her experiences. (Avcı, Çekin, Tahiroğlu, 2008, s. 1-7)

For this reason, he/she keeps his/her experiences to himself/herself, fearing that adults will blame him/her or not believe what he/she tells them. Often the child may begin to withdraw from the people around him/her. He/she may feel that the adults who care for him/her do not or cannot protect him/her. After abuse, these children may become overly interested in sexuality, exhibit sexual behaviors, increase sexual play, show masturbation behavior and this may cause damage to their genitals.

4.5. Helping Sexually Abused Children with Expert Assistance

It is inevitable to get help from an expert in sexual abuse, which causes many psychological and medical damages in children. In this process, it is important to know the age, level and developmental characteristics of the child. The language of communication determines the child's perspective on therapy. Apart from the therapy method conducted by the expert, there are treatment methods that the family should apply at home. In this process, it is important to listen to the specialist and to act in common. Believing the child's narrations at first, not giving exaggerated reactions that would cause the child to be scared and anxious, reassuring the child that it is not his/her fault and that everything will be alright, assuring the child that you will help him/her and that he/she will be safe, not forcing the child to talk about the issue, but listening if the child wants to talk about it. Not commenting on the story of abuse told by the child in any way, if the child has developed beliefs that he/she deserved this event, telling him/her that it is not his/her fault in any way, asking questions based on emotions rather than curiosity, preparing the child for what will happen by giving information about what will happen after the situation is revealed, keeping the situation only among the primary people so

that the child is not socially stigmatized, informing the child what his/her rights are, what he/she can do and what the consequences of the behavior he/she decides to do will be, and guiding families to develop positive behavior with these items by the expert will be very useful.

5. Psychological - Emotional Neglect and Abused Children

Psychological-emotional abuse is defined as harming the child due to some behaviors, attitudes and reactions of the people who are responsible for taking care of the child and psychologically damaging the child by depriving him/her of the attention and love he/she needs. These behaviors are conducted by the person or persons who have power over the child or young person with characteristics such as age, interest, level, knowledge and position. Such behaviors cause the child's development process to be negatively affected. Emotional abuse can occur alone or in combination with physical and sexual abuse. Emotional abuse may continue even after the visible problems of physical and sexual abuse have disappeared. When talking about psychological-emotional abuse against children, we should first look at the behavior of the parents. Parents' attitudes towards their children are influenced by their personality traits, the socio-economic conditions in which they grew up, their level of education and the traditional child-rearing techniques of the society in which they live.

5.1. Symptoms and Consequences of Psychological-Emotional Neglect and Abuse

Symptoms of Psychological-Emotional Neglect and Abuse; Rejecting every behavior, not caring about anything, not caring, aggression, behavioral disorders. *Consequences of Psychological-Emotional Neglect and Abuse;* Lack of confidence, weakness in self-esteem, introversion, lack of development of basic skills, alcohol or substance abuse, suicide and difficulty in establishing relationships, destructive behaviors are factors among the consequences of emotional and psychological abuse. Psychological-emotional abuse leaves negative marks on the child's development in later periods. (Evans, Burton, 2013, s. 231-245)

5.2. Types of Psychological-Emotional Neglect and Abuse

Behaviors defined as psychological-emotional abuse are negative attitudes and behaviors such as witnessing domestic violence, comparison, rejection, isolation, overprotection, excessive tolerance, pressure, deprivation of love and stimuli, constant criticism, humiliation, threats, blaming, ignoring, and expecting responsibilities inappropriate for the child's age and characteristics. In this type of abuse, the age, level and developmental level of the individual is important. For example, while overprotectiveness in infancy and early childhood is considered a normal behavior and a necessity, the same type of behavior can be called emotional and psychological abuse in childhood and adolescence. What is important here is empathy. While parents' tolerance towards adolescents and their acceptance of them as they are leads to positive results in adolescents and children, their attitudes such as excessive tolerance and indulgence, overprotection, rejection, oppression, obedience to children, separation of children and dependency lead to negative results in adolescents and children. Behaviors that cause psychological-emotional abuse are defined as rejection, humiliation, intimidation, isolation, directing to crime, refusal to respond emotionally. *Rejection*: is when the child is not accepted at home, his/her emotional needs are not met, he/she is ignored, the child is held responsible for every negative situation at home, and his/her existence. Children who are not psychologically accepted by their parents face behavioral problems because they cannot achieve secure bonding. *Humiliation*: is when the parents behave in a way that causes the child to be offended, humiliated, or humiliates his/her pride, use nicknames, make statements that create a sense of inadequacy in the child, and say harsh words. *Intimidation*: Intimidation is a method that has very lasting consequences. Educational methods that intimidate and make the child uneasy by saying "If you do this, you will be petrified, if you upset me, you will be left without a mother, you will grow up in the hands of a stepmother, then you will understand my value" have worse and permanent consequences in the emotional world of the child. *Isolation*: It is the punishment of children by leaving them alone from an early age and taking them away from their friends. Isolation is not limited to spatial conditions. Oppressive and authoritarian attitudes towards the child withdraw the child from social life. Situations such as not allowing the child to bring friends home, spending time with friends and preventing the child from participating in school activities can also be included in isolation. *Orientation to Crime*; It is the tolerance of the child's attitudes that do not obey the rules of

society, encouraging these behaviors, not teaching the child concepts such as good, bad, acceptance and rejection, and directing the child to that path by showing bad examples. Guilt behavior develops in early childhood and is a lifelong process. *Emotional Barrier*: It is the situation when the emotional needs of the child and the necessary needs such as attention, love, affection and being with the child are not met. Children who lack the support and attention of the family feel invisible, cannot develop a positive identity or have negative feelings about themselves.

5.3. Helping Psychological-Emotional Neglect and Abused Children with Expert Assistance

Psychological-emotional abuse is more complex than other forms of abuse. It is difficult to directly measure the consequences of this type of abuse. However, this type of abuse, especially when performed by the parents, causes pauses and delays in the psychological and social development of the child. This type of neglect and abuse has a greater long-term psychological impact on children than other types of neglect and abuse. In children exposed to emotional abuse and neglect, there may be difficulties in communication, difficulties in self-expression, externalizing and internalizing problems, decreased self-confidence, suicidal behavior, childhood masturbation, finger sucking, biting, shaking, bedwetting and encopresis, eating disorders, lack of confidence, hyperactivity, introversion, feelings of powerlessness, aggression, excessive passivity, Anti-social behaviors such as thieving, lying, poor pregnancy and baby care, inadequate stimulation, neurological deficiencies such as malnutrition and inappropriate medical care, negative self-concept, depression, sleep disorders, excessive anxiety, phobias, dependent and avoidant personality disorders and many other psychiatric disorders can be seen. In these situations, it is necessary to work primarily with the attitudes of the parents and to conduct therapies aimed at developing the child's positive personality traits with the help of experts in the field.

6. Economically Abused Children

It is the situation when the person in charge of taking care of the child, most often the parents, sees the child as a source of financial income and forces the child to work to gain income from the child. Parents may use their children to satisfy their desire to earn a lot of money. Making money from the child by giving him/her more burdens than he/she can do is considered as a type of economic abuse. Neglect is when those who are responsible for meeting the basic needs of the child do not meet these requirements. For example, medical neglect includes not taking the child to the hospital when he/she is sick, and educational neglect includes not sending the child to school even though he/she is old enough.

6.1. Causes and Consequences of Economic Abuse

When we look at the causes of economic abuse, When we look at the causes of economic abuse, factors such as social, economic and cultural problems, injustice in income distribution, increase in poverty, migration from villages to cities, illegal harbor, cheap child labor come to the fore. As for the consequences of economic abuse, it is seen that children are deprived of these rights at an age when they would play with their peers and receive education, they may experience health problems due to working in unhealthy conditions, and their development is negatively affected due to working in workplaces with unsuitable conditions at young ages.

6.2. Types of Economic Abuse

Kidnapping of Children; It is the forced abduction of a child for the purpose of lying, deception, using force, frightening, threatening, sexual harassment and slavery. Today, kidnapping of children has become an international problem. Within the borders of the country, kidnapping occurs from rural areas to cities, touristic cities, areas where construction works are intensive. In cross-border kidnapping, the child is taken from his/her own country to another country. Child labor is the forced labor of children at low wages in jobs that prevent them in all areas of development and violate their rights. Child labor is mostly seen in agriculture. Migration from rural to urban areas, poverty, crowded families, illegal labor and the preference of employers for child labor due to its cheapness are the main reasons for child labor.

6.3. Helping Economically Exploited Children With An Expert

Economically abused children usually come from families with low socio-economic status. Most families migrating from rural areas to urban areas deliver their children into the hands of people who aim to employ cheap labor. The biggest reason for this is often the desire of the parents to see the child as a source of financial income and to gain profit from him/her. It is inevitable to take protective measures for children in this situation. These protective measures taken by experts in the field include efforts aiming to prevent the emergence of violence, early diagnosis, treatment studies and rehabilitation efforts for children who have been exposed to economic exploitation.

7. Conclusion

Child neglect and abuse is a social problem that is as old and well-known as the history of humanity but is less likely to be occurred. The most important people here are the parents, who have the biggest role in the child's life. Undoubtedly, most individuals who get married want to have children after a while. Those who decide to have a child should think carefully about the responsibility they will take, the order to be established, effective communication and socio-economic and cultural conditions. After the child is born, it is especially important to maintain a good balance of power and control in interpersonal relationships. Otherwise, physical, psychological-emotional, sexual and economic damages are inevitable. Neglect and abuse can threaten the physical, emotional, economic and sexual safety of children and cause behaviors that negatively affect their lives. Children exposed to neglect and abuse may develop negative behaviors, deterioration in social relations, unhealthy thinking, tendency to commit crimes, major depression, and physical injuries may occur. Therefore, it is important for every child who has been neglected and abused to receive help and support from experts in their field to prevent other psychiatric disorders that may occur due to psychological trauma, to protect themselves physically, sexually, economically and emotionally, and to be enlightened about where and how to apply after abuse.

8. References

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